

The Influence of The use of Google and Libraries on Students' Learning Outcomes in Social Subjects Class VII of SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research uses quantitative descriptive research. Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar with a total of 171 students constitute the population in this study. Sampling in this study used a total sampling technique. By using this sampling technique, the students who will be the samples in this study were 171 students consisting of classes VIII-1, VIII-2, VIII-3, VIII- 4, VIII-5. Data collection techniques use questionnaires and documentation. The hypothesis making technique uses multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this study show that: 1) There is a positive and significant influence from the use of Google on the learning outcomes of social studies subjects, seen from the t test where the t_{value} from the use of Google (16.394) > t_{table} value (1.65381) which means this variable significant. 2) There is a positive and significant influence from the library on the learning outcomes of social studies subjects, seen from the t test where the value of library t_{count} (12.658) > t_{table} (1.65381) which means the variable is significant. 3) the use of Google and libraries together influences the learning outcomes of social studies subjects, seen from the Ftest where the F_{count} value (330.329) > F_{table} value (3.048). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.797, which means that 79.7% of the Google and library utilization variables influence the learning outcomes of social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 20.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research. The regression value is 2149.521, while the residual value is 546.607, which means there are other factors that influence the learning outcomes of social studies subjects but were not studied in this study, namely 546.607. The results of the multiple regression analysis test are $Y = 21.777 + 0.401X_1 + 0.299X_2 + 546.607$, which means that variable X_1 (use of Google) with a value of 0.401 has a more dominant influence than variable X_2 (library) with a value of 0.299.

INTRODUCTION

One of the keys to success is being sensitive to information. The success or failure of the teaching and learning process influences how Google is used in learning and libraries at school.

In today's advanced era, new things are discovered every day. Not only product innovation makes human life easier, but science has also experienced many significant advances. These changes are always reported to the public on an ongoing basis. Usually internet media is the first media to publish these advances. With the internet, Google search engine technology can access information, not only millions, but even billions of information in the internet world that can be accessed.

Google is known as a search engine that is more popular among netters (one term for internet users) because of its efficiency in searching plus the speed of getting results, as well as other features that satisfy its users, which causes netizens to choose it. That's why Google is the most frequently accessed when surfing the internet.

There is no need to debate anymore, Google is currently on the rise and is widely used specifically in the world of education. Various information about the world of education can be obtained easily. Especially students, they will visit the Google search engine to look for information or materials to complete school assignments.

For students, the presence of Google has brought many conveniences in finding the information they need, either to increase their insight or to complete assignments. It cannot be denied, as a student who is in an educational institution or what is called a school, there is no such thing as a library.

It cannot be denied, however, that libraries are the heart of an educational institution. The parable of the library as the heart of an educational institution identifies that the existence of a library is very important and plays a very important role in supporting the education, teaching and learning and research processes.

The library is the heart of an educational institution, so library users are required to master the various knowledge and skills needed to be able to use or utilize various library facilities effectively. This skill not only concerns the ability to read or understand information, but also to search, find and select information among the pile of materials and the explosion of information in this era of globalization.

Based on the researcher's experience while carrying out PPL (Practical Field Experience) at SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar, the researcher saw that the majority of students had learning outcomes that were not optimal, as evidenced by low test scores. The reason this happens is due to many factors. It's probably because you forget your assignments, so you forget yourself when surfing the internet, you don't access Google to complete your school assignments, but you play games or other social media, so you forget your assignments and end up copying other friends' assignments or not even doing your assignments.

In fact, homework assignments are given with the aim that students can remember or repeat lesson material that has taken place at school. Using Google, students get information about the subject matter that will be taught at the next meeting so that when asked by the teacher, students are ready to answer. It's a shame

that only some students are aware of this, that's what causes poor information and therefore poor knowledge.

In the learning process activities at school, Google has not been utilized optimally because WiFi access is limited for students. There is an option to find learning resources, namely the school library. Library in junior high school Negeri 6 has not yet been utilized optimally by students, seen from the condition of the library which is still inadequate and the lack of visitors in the library.

The teaching and learning process is said to be successful if the students' learning outcomes are able to achieve and pass the Minimum Requirements Criteria (KKM) that have been determined by the school. Student learning outcomes can be seen from student test scores. Based on the results of observations, it is known that the KKM for social studies subjects is 65. For more details, see the table below.

Table 1.1. Daily Test Scores for Class VII IPS

No.	Class	Number of students	Daily Test Scores			
			<65	%	>65	%
1	VIII-1	34	9	26%	25	74%
2	VIII-2	35	10	29%	25	71%
3	VIII-3	34	7	21%	27	79%
4	VIII-4	34	8	24%	26	76%
5	VIII-5	34	7	21%	27	79%
Total		171	41		130	

(Source: list of daily test scores for T.A. 2022/2023)

In table 1.1 above it can be seen that the learning outcomes of class VIII students are not optimal. There is a deviation between expectations and reality. Of the 171 total number of class VIII students, it is hoped that 90% of class VIII students for social studies subjects will achieve a KKM score of 65, namely 154 students, but in reality, seen from the learning results obtained, there are only 130 class VIII students who achieve the KKM score for social studies subjects, it is said to be far from expectations.

Therefore, in this research, the use of Google and libraries is an important factor in improving student learning outcomes optimally at SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar.

Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting research with the title " **The Influence Of The Use Of Google And Libraries On Students' Learning Outcomes In Social Subjects Class Viii Of Smp Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar** ".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Utilization of Google

2.1.1. Understanding Google

Google has an abbreviation, namely Global Organization of Oriented Group Language of Earth. According to JUD (2009:16) "Google is a leading company that is very famous for its search engine." Using Google, internet users can carry out various kinds of searches in cyberspace such as searching for information, articles, images, maps or even just answers to simple crossword clues.

According to M. Agus and J. Alam (2006:33) "Google is the most favorite search engine for netizens (one of the terms internet users)". According to Asep Hapidin (2009:9) "Google is the most widely used search engine". Moreover, there are many online services and products that can be used, such as email accounts, web browsers, productivity software, mobile phones and applications, mapping tools, e-books, internet advertising, as well as various video and other social networking sites.

Google's main mission is to gather the world and make it accessible and useful to everyone. In carrying out this mission, Google continues to innovate to provide services that make it easier to access and manage information for users around the world. The Google search engine strives to provide information relevantly, accurately and quickly to billions of people around the world.

2.1.2. Types of Google

According to JUD (2009:17) the types of Google are as follows:

1. Google Search

Google search is the most up-to-date with millions of users every day or it could be said to be the most widely used because it is able to provide accurate information on the keywords being searched for.

2. Google earth

Displays various data obtained from NASA such as weather and 3D images.

3. Google mail

Similar to the e-mail service owned by Yahoo!, Google also has its own e-mail service and if you have a Google mail account then all other Google products will also be integrated with Google mail.

4. Google chrome

As the name suggests, Google Chrome, which was created and developed by Google, is one of the most popular browsers because of the many features available and the speed of response it has.

So the suitability of Google referred to by researchers from the four types of Google above for social studies subjects is Google search and Google chrome which are used by students to search for information related to social studies subjects.

According to Team Cyber (2010:12) "Google search and Google chrome, which were developed by Google, are widely accessed by people because they have a simple appearance and are easy to understand even for ordinary people, and also provide maximum search results compared to other search engines."

2.1.3. Factors Affecting Google Utilization

According to Sukindar (2023:1) there are factors that influence the use of Google, namely as follows:

1. Powerful network

Accessing Google requires good connection support. When there is a problem with the internet connection, such as being disconnected or blocked, the service will not be able to be opened no matter what device or service is used. Switching to a faster and more stable connection is often necessary so that services can run more smoothly.

2. Application or system supports

Up to the latest version of the application or operating system is important so that later you will continue to get various kinds of support to access a number of services, including Google, among others.

2.1.4. Google Utilization Indicators

According to Lovata Andrian (2023:1) Google utilization indicators are as follows:

1. Highly relevant results

Google is a search service that can produce relevant information according to your needs its users. Of course, the information offered is also very complete, ranging from news articles, entertainment to learning materials.

2. Very fast search

Apart from very relevant results, the Google search engine is also able to quickly find the information its users need. Especially when searching using relevant keywords, this service only takes 0.5 seconds to display millions of results in the search.

3. Simple appearance

Google provides a basic and simple design, but still pleasant and without too many ads that can sometimes be annoying.

4. Various files are indexed on Google

Google is one of the search engines that is widely used by internet users because it has many advantages, such as being able to index various types of files such as PDF, Doc, Power Point and others. This can meet the information demands of users who want certain file formats.

5. Dynamic

Dynamic is a general term that refers to anything or conditions that are constantly changing, moving actively and experiencing significant development.

Search engines must have dynamic algorithms so that the information produced is relevant. Considering the many concerns from users regarding the results they will get, the Google search engine continues to update its algorithm so that it remains ideal in its class.

2.2. Library

2.2.1. Definition of Library

Library comes from the word library, which means books, books and printed books. According to Hamid Sakti Wibowo (2023:4) "A library is an institution or place used to store and lend books and other library materials such as magazines, journals, newspapers and other information media."

The meaning of library has changed and developed in accordance with science and information technology. Based on a simple definition, a library is defined as a collection of books or a physical building where books are collected and arranged according to a certain system for the benefit of users.

2.2.2. Types of Libraries

According to Peppy Rizma (2022:1) the types of libraries are as follows:

1. School library

The first type of library is the school library. School libraries are one of the facilities available in almost all schools in Indonesia, from elementary to high school levels. In general, school libraries provide books that support learning, in this way the teaching and learning process can run more effectively and efficiently. We can come to the library during school hours to read or borrow books, we can also use the library for group study or discussions.

2. College library

Not only in schools, libraries can also be found in universities. The college library also has a very complete book collection. Apart from that, it also has a collection of theses from students who have graduated. The existence of a library at this university supports the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, namely education, research and community service.

3. Public library

This library is intended for the public, so pupils, students or the general public can enter this library, that way this library is never empty of visitors who want to read the books in its collection. Usually the book collection at a public library can also be borrowed as long as you have a membership card.

4. Special library

This special library is a type of library managed by private or government institutions. It is said to be a special library because it is only intended for certain people, for example only for the parent agency and the like, so if you are not a member you cannot access the books in it.

5. Regional library

The type of library that can be found in Indonesia is a regional library. The number of regional libraries in Indonesia is not as large as school libraries or university libraries. This is because usually in one district or city there is only one regional library. Need it is known that this library is managed or managed by the local government.

6. National library

A national library is a central library in a country whose existence functions as a supervisor for libraries and publications in its territory. The national library in Indonesia has a very large collection of books, the total collection reaches 2.6 million copies. National libraries have many obligations, such as storing every library published in a country, compiling a national bibliography, being an information center for the country concerned, collecting other published library materials about that country and much more.

7. Mobile library

This type of library is part of a public library but users who come to readers use vehicles. Not all mobile libraries in Indonesia belong to public libraries, some are also owned by certain organizations or communities. Mobile libraries have the same function as public libraries. The form of service is different because the mobile library uses the pick-up and drop-off method and the book collection it has is also smaller.

8. International library

As the name suggests, an international library means a library founded by 2 or more countries, or a library that is part of an international organization. The duties, services and collections of international libraries vary depending on the type and objectives of the owning institution. The suitability of the library referred to by researchers from the eight types of libraries above is school libraries. According to Dian Sinaga (2007:16) "The school library is an educational facility that also determines the achievements of the institution that supports it. Therefore, school libraries must be created in such a way that they truly function as a support for the teaching and learning process."

2.2.3. Factors Affecting School Libraries

According to Shabri Shaleh Anwar (2016:196-201) the factors that influence libraries in schools are as follows:

1. Students' interests

The interest factor of students is very determining in the use of the school library, because students have personal awareness as a driving force in their souls to use the school library for the smooth running of their studies. If the students are interested, especially in reading the books available in the school library, the school library will automatically help in the smooth running of the students' learning activities, because no matter how complete and good the facilities in the school library are, they will not be as useful as they are intended to be. It is desirable if the students have no interest in using it, especially the students' interest in reading library books.

2. Management staff

In general, library management in schools is handed over to one of the teachers who is given the responsibility of managing the library in addition to his main teaching duties. Managers must be aware of the importance and position of libraries for students, understand the needs of students.

3. Library collections

The condition of the library collection is actually closely related to the purpose of establishing a school library. Regarding collections in the form of books, a school library at least requires mandatory student handbooks, books that complement student learning and teacher handbooks for teaching. The library materials owned by the library must be able to support the teaching and learning process, so when procuring library materials you should consider the school curriculum, as well as the tastes of the readers, in this case the students.

4. Teacher motivation

Teacher motivation needs to be paid attention to, because to arouse or excite students towards the library, teacher assistance is needed as encouragement, motivation, so that positive motives are aroused and/or enhanced within the child.

5. Library buildings and facilities

Regarding the condition of the library building, what must be considered is the location, number of rooms and layout, which need to be considered when establishing a school library, namely:

a. Location

The library is in the middle of where school activities take place, so it is easy to reach from all directions.

b. Construction/condition of the building

Able to withstand the weight of furniture and its contents, fireproof and burnt-resistant, with enough gaps to provide natural lighting and without lots of poles and partitions.

c. Room setup

It depends on the area and shape of the room, and for ease of service, but attention must also be paid to architectural aspects, ventilation comfort, freshness of the room and its beauty. Apart from buildings, school library facilities are important, what is meant is all the equipment used in running a school library apart from books and library materials. This equipment or facilities includes bookshelves, newspaper racks, magazine racks, drawing

cabinets, circulation tables, catalog cupboards or cabinets, display boards, notice boards, cassette tape boxes, reading tables and other equipment that is used indirectly.

2.2.4. School Library Indicators

School library indicators are measures or markers used to evaluate the performance and effectiveness of libraries in supporting the learning process, literacy development and education in schools. This indicator helps in assessing the extent to which the school library can achieve educational goals and provide benefits to students.

According to Abi Haura (2013:8) school library indicators include:

1. School library collection

The number and variety of books and sources of information in the library. This indicator includes textbooks, references, fiction, non-fiction, magazines, and others.

2. Rules and regulations in the school library

The extent to which students and school staff can access the library, both in terms of location, opening hours, and rules for borrowing and returning books.

3. Student visits to the school library

Student visits to the school library are a benchmark for student use of the library.

4. Reading ability

Evaluation of students' reading abilities as an impact of library use.

5. Technology and digital resources

Evaluate the availability and use of digital resources, such as e-books, online databases, and other technology tools.

6. User Satisfaction

Surveys and feedback from students, teachers, and staff about their satisfaction with library services.

2.3. Learning outcomes

2.3.1. Understanding Learning Outcomes

According to Hasrian Rudi Setiawan and Achmad Bahtiar (2023:23) "Learning outcomes are abilities obtained by students through learning activities". According to Purwanto (in Umi Kulsum, 2023:10) "Learning outcomes are the results obtained by students after carrying out learning activities, in the form of affective, cognitive and psychomotor".

Based on several opinions above, learning outcomes can be interpreted as the results achieved by students in learning, which shows the level of students' abilities in following the learning program within a certain time according to the predetermined curriculum. These learning outcomes are often reflected as grades (learning outcomes) which determine whether students are successful in learning.

2.3.2. Types of Learning Outcomes

According to Umi Kulsum (2023:10) classifies the types of learning outcomes as follows:.

1. Cognitive domain (cognitive area)
Behavior is a process of thinking or behavior that is the result of the brain's work. Several cognitive abilities include knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation.
2. Affective domain (affective area)
Behavior that appears in a person as a sign of his tendency to make choices or decisions to testify in a certain environment. The affective area is divided into 5 levels, namely receiving, responding, valuing, organizing and characterization.
3. Psychomotor domain (psychomotor area)
Behavior that arises from the work of the human body's functions.

2.3.3. Factors that Influence Learning Outcomes

According to Djamarah (in Arsyi Mirdanda, 2018:36-37) there are two factors that influence learning outcomes, namely:

1. Internal factors

Internal factors or factors that originate from within the student. These factors can be classified into two, namely physiological factors and psychological factors. Category of physiological factors between others are the physical condition of students, the condition of their five senses. The categories of psychological factors are intelligence, talent, interests, motivation, and cognitive abilities.

2. External factors

Factors originating from outside the student. Classified into two, namely environmental factors and instrumental factors. The environmental factor category is the natural environment such as family, school, peers and socio-cultural environment such as values and norms; Language; traditions and customs; religion and belief. The instrumental factor categories are curriculum, programs, facilities and infrastructure, and teachers.

2.3.4. Learning Outcome Indicators

According to Lasmana Aan (in Ibnu Mahtumi, et al, 2022: 17-19) the learning outcome indicators are as follows:

1. Cognitive (creative domain) includes:
 - a. Observation, meaning it can show comparisons and connections.
 - b. Memory, meaning it can show again.
 - c. Understanding, meaning being able to explain and interpret in your own language.
 - d. Application/application, meaning providing the right example.
 - e. Analysis (careful examination and sorting), means the activity of describing and classifying.
 - f. Synthesis (making a new and complete alloy), means being able to connect materials and make them whole.
2. Affective (taste domain) includes:
 - a. Acceptance, meaning being able to show an attitude of acceptance and rejection.
 - b. Welcome, meaning willingness to participate and take advantage.
 - c. Appreciation (appreciative attitude), means considering it important, useful, beautiful, harmonious, admiring.
 - d. Internalization (deepening), meaning following, believing, and denying.

- e. Characterization (perception), meaning that indicators can be institutionalized or eliminated, manifested in personal and daily behavior.
- 3. Psychomotor (domain of intention) includes:
 - a. Skills, moving and acting with indicators of ability to coordinate the movements of all body parts.
 - b. Verbal and non-verbal expression skills, with indicators of fluency in pronouncing, making mimics and physical movements.

2.5. Conceptual framework

Based on variable theories regarding the use of Google and libraries, it seems that there is an influence on the learning outcomes of IPS subjects for class VIII students at SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar, both together and individually.

This conceptual framework can be explained through the following image:

Figure 2.1. Conceptual framework

(Source: processed by researchers, 2023)

METHODS

The type of research carried out is quantitative descriptive research. According to Rita Yuningsih (2023:57) "Quantitative descriptive research is research that describes and interprets objects according to the data collected in quantitative research". Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar with a total of 171 students constitute the population in this study. Sampling in this study used a total sampling technique. By using this sampling technique, the students who will be the samples in this study were 171 students consisting of classes VIII-1, VIII-2, VIII-3, VIII- 4, VIII-5. Data collection techniques use questionnaires and documentation. The hypothesis making technique uses multiple linear regression analysis.

RESULTS

The results of this study show that there is a positive and significant influence from the use of Google on the learning outcomes of social studies subjects. There is a positive and significant influence from the library on the learning outcomes of social studies subjects. Proven by the following calculation results:

Table 4.1. T Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21,777	2,152		10,119	,000
	Utilization of Google	,401	,024	,609	16,394	,000
	Library	,299	,024	,471	12,658	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

(Source: SPSS version 24)

Seen from the t test where the t_{value} from the use of Google (16.394) > t_{table} value (1.65381) which means this variable significant. Seen from the t test where the value of library t_{count} (12.658) > t_{table} (1.65381) which means the variable is significant.

The use of Google and libraries together influences the learning outcomes of social studies subjects. Proven by the following calculation results:

Tabel 4.2. F Test Results

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2149,521	2	1074,761	330,329	,000 ^b
	Residual	546,607	168	3,254		
	Total	2696,128	170			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

b. Predictors: (Constant), Library, Utilization of Google

(Source: SPSS version 24)

Seen from the Ftest where the F_{count} value (330.329) > F_{table} value (3.048).

Tabel 4.3. Determination Coefficient Test Results

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,893 ^a	,797	,795	1,804

a. Predictors: (Constant), Library, Utilization of Google

b. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

(Source: SPSS version 24)

The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.797, which means that 79.7% of the Google and library utilization variables influence the learning outcomes of social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 20.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

Tabel 4.4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21,777	2,152		10,119	,000
	Utilization of Google	,401	,024	,609	16,394	,000
	Library	,299	,024	,471	12,658	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

(Source: SPSS version 24)

The regression value is 2149.521, while the residual value is 546.607, which means there are other factors that influence the learning outcomes of social studies subjects but were not studied in this study, namely 546.607. The results of the multiple regression analysis test are $Y = 21.777 + 0.401X_1 + 0.299X_2 + 546.607$, which means that

variable X_1 (use of Google) with a value of 0.401 has a more dominant influence than variable X_2 (library) with a value of 0.299.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

From the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a positive and significant influence from the use of Google on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the significant value is $0.00 < 0.05$ and the calculated t value from Google utilization (16.394) > ttable value (1.65381) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence on students' social patterns on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the tcount value from the library (12.658) > ttable (1.65381) which means this variable is significant.
3. Using Google and libraries together influences learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (330,329) > Ftable value (3,048). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.797. Which means that 79.7% of the variables using Google and the library have an influence on student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 20.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

Recommendations

The suggestions in this research are:

1. For schools, it is hoped that they can implement programs on how to use Google properly with students and add book collections to the school library so that students are active in reading.
2. Teachers are expected to work together to direct students to be careful when using the internet, open Google for learning purposes and remind students that the school library is very important for learning.
3. For future researchers, further research needs to be conducted to find out other factors not examined in this research that influence social studies learning outcomes, because social studies learning outcomes do not only influence Google and library utilization factors. It can be seen from the information in this research that this research provides information that the use of Google and libraries has an influence on the learning outcomes of social studies subjects in class VIII of SMP Negeri 6 Pematang Siantar by 79.7% and the remaining 20.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research. . The aim is to be able to add new knowledge that is important for students' success in achieving the expected learning outcomes.

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